

ASSESSMENT OF ASCORBIC ACID MEDIATED PROTECTION AGAINST DICHLORVOS INDUCED SPLEEN TOXICITY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the protective effects of ascorbic acid on the spleen of adult male Wistar rats exposed to dichlorvos (DDVP), a widely used organophosphate insecticide commonly marketed as Sniper. Dichlorvos is known to induce toxicity through oxidative stress and disruption of normal cellular functions, potentially affecting vital organs including the spleen. A total of thirty-six adult male Wistar rats weighing 180–250 g were used for the experiment and randomly divided into six groups: control, dichlorvos only, low dose ascorbic acid + dichlorvos, low dose ascorbic acid only, high dose ascorbic acid + dichlorvos, and high dose ascorbic acid only. The experiment lasted eight weeks, including two weeks of acclimatization and six weeks of oral administration of dichlorvos and/or ascorbic acid. Parameters assessed included body weight, spleen weight, hematological indices, oxidative stress biomarkers, and histological examination of spleen tissue. Results showed that dichlorvos exposure produced mild

alterations in some hematological parameters and increased oxidative stress markers, while administration of ascorbic acid demonstrated a moderating effect. However, statistical analysis revealed no significant differences in spleen weight and most hematological parameters across the experimental groups ($p > 0.05$). Histological observations suggested that ascorbic acid may help preserve splenic architecture and reduce potential oxidative damage induced by dichlorvos. In conclusion, the findings suggest that ascorbic acid possesses protective antioxidant properties that may mitigate the toxic effects of dichlorvos on the spleen. These results highlight the potential role of antioxidant supplementation in reducing pesticide-induced organ toxicity and contribute to the understanding of preventive strategies against organophosphate exposure.

INTRODUCTION

Pesticides are chemical substances used to control or eliminate organisms that are harmful to crops, animals, and humans. They play an important role in agriculture and food preservation, but their widespread use has raised concerns about their potential toxic effects on humans, animals, and the environment (Ogeleka et al., 2020).

Dichlorvos (2,2-dichlorovinyl dimethyl phosphate; DDVP) is an organophosphate insecticide commonly used for pest control in homes, farms, and food storage facilities. It is widely sold under different trade names such as Nuvan, DD-Force, and Sniper (Fayinminnu et al., 2022). In Nigeria, Sniper is commonly used due to its affordability and effectiveness against household pests (Ozoemena et al., 2021).

However, dichlorvos is classified by the World Health Organization as a highly hazardous chemical and its misuse has raised significant public health concerns (WHO, 1992).

Dichlorvos exerts its toxic effects mainly by inhibiting acetylcholinesterase, leading to the accumulation of acetylcholine in nerve synapses and overstimulation of the nervous system (Veeraiah et al., 2015). In addition to its neurotoxic effects, exposure to dichlorvos can also cause oxidative stress by generating reactive oxygen species, which may damage cellular structures and organs (Lushchak, 2011).

The spleen is an important lymphoid organ involved in immune defense, blood filtration, and removal of damaged red blood cells. Due to its role in immune surveillance and high metabolic activity, the spleen is susceptible to damage caused by toxic substances such as

pesticides (Lewis et al., 2013; Patel et al., 2021).

Ascorbic acid (vitamin C) is a water-soluble antioxidant that helps protect cells from oxidative damage by neutralizing free radicals and supporting the body's antioxidant defense system (Omotayo et al., 2021). Studies suggest that ascorbic acid supplementation may reduce oxidative stress and protect tissues from toxic agents (Dlamini et al., 2022).

Therefore, this study aims to investigate the effect of ascorbic acid administration on the spleen of adult male Wistar rats exposed to dichlorvos.

MATERIALS AND METHOD OF STUDY

ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical approval was obtained from the institute animal ethics committee, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, College of Health Science, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Anambra state.

MATERIAL

1. 36 Adult male Rat
2. Dichlorvos
3. Abscorbic Acid Tablet
4. Distilled water
5. syringe
6. surgical gloves
7. metal plate
8. spoon
9. storage container

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

The experiment lasted for a period of 8 weeks; two (2) weeks for acclimatization and six weeks for administration of dichlorvos and ascorbic and were given through the oral route. The animals were randomly grouped as follows:

Group A: Served as the control group and received normal feed and water daily ad libitum throughout the period of experiment (6 weeks).

Group B: (Dichlorvos only group); Administered dichlorvos orally at a dose of 0.1ml daily, rat chow and distilled water for 6 weeks. The rats were administered 20mg/kg body weight once daily.

Group C: (Low dose of ascorbic acid+ dichlorvos); Administered ascorbic acid and dichlorvos orally at a dose of 0.4ml and 0.1ml daily, respectively. They were given rat chow and distilled water for 6 weeks. The rats were administered 50mg/kg body weight of ascorbic acid and 20mg/kg body weight of dichlorvos once daily.

Group D: (Low dose of ascorbic acid only); Administered ascorbic acid orally at a dose of 0.1ml, feed and distilled water daily for 6 weeks. The rats received 50mg/kg body weight of ascorbic acid once daily.

Group E: (High dose of ascorbic acid + dichlorvos); Administered ascorbic acid at 0.4ml and dichlorvos at 0.1ml orally, were fed with rat chow and provided with distilled water daily for 6 weeks. They were administered 150mg/kg body weight of ascorbic acid and 20mg/kg body weight of dichlorvos once daily.

Group F: (High dose of ascorbic acid only); Administered ascorbic acid at a dose of 0.4ml, received rat chow and provided with distilled water daily for 6 weeks. The rats were administered 150mg/kg body weight of ascorbic acid once daily.

At the end of administration, three rats from each group were weighed with a weighing balance and sacrificed. Blood samples were collected by decapitation into EDTA tubes and plain tubes.

Oxidative Stress Biomarkers

Estimation of lipid peroxidation(Malondialdehyde, MDA)

Lipid peroxidation was estimated by determination of malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in serum using the thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) method.

Malondialdehyde (MDA)

Malondialdehyde MDA level was determined by using UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Model 752G, China) according to the method of Alam and Fareed, (2016). Malondialdehyde (MDA) is a product of lipid peroxidation. When heated with 2-thiobarbituric acid (TBA) under alkaline condition, it forms a pink coloured product, which has an absorption maximum at 532 M. The intensity of colour generated is directly proportional to the concentration of MDA in the sample.

Reagents Used

1. 2-thiobarbituric acid (TBA) dissolved in alkaline medium (sodium hydroxide)
2. Glacial acetic acid

3. Serum sample (test)
4. Blank solution (distilled water in place of serum)
5. Distilled water

Procedure

1. To 0.1ml of sample (serum) in the test tube was added 1ml of thiobarbituric acid dissolved in alkaline medium (sodiumhydroxide).
2. The mixture was mixed thoroughly, and 1ml of glacialacetic acid was added to the mixture.
3. The reaction mixture was also shaken thoroughly and incubated in boiling water (1000C) for 15 minutes
4. During heating, a pink coloured product was formed.
5. It was allowed to cool and the turbidity removed by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes at 25°C.
6. Thereafter, the absorbance of the supernatant was read at 532nm.
7. The same volume of TBA and glacial acetic acid was addedto the blank, but 0.1ml of distilled water was added to theblank instead of plasma.
8. The level of MDA in the serum is expressed as nmol/mlusing the molar extinction coefficient for MDA ($1.56 \times 10^5 \text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$).

Calculation

$$\text{MDA (nmol/ml)} = (\text{OD} \times 1000000) / E532$$

Where

E532 = Molar extinction coefficient for MDA ($1.56 \times 10^5 \text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)

Determination of Serum Superoxide Dismutase(SOD) Activities

Superoxide dismutase was assayed by using UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Model 752G, China) according to the standard method of Rotruk *et al.*, (1993). The ability of superoxide dismutase (SOD) to inhibit the autoxidation of adrenaline at pH 10.2 makes this reaction a basis for the SOD assay. Superoxide anion (O_2^-) generated by the xanthineoxidase reaction is known to cause the oxidation of adrenaline to adrenochrome. The yield of adrenochrome produced per superoxide anion introduced increased with increasing pH and concentration of adrenaline.

Reagents Used

1. Carbonate buffer (pH 10.2)
2. Freshly prepared epinephrine (adrenaline) solution
3. Distilled water
4. Serum sample (test)
5. Blank solution (distilled water in place of serum)

Procedure

1. To 80 μ l of sample/blank in a clean test tube was added 1000 μ l of carbonate buffer (pH 10.2).
2. The resulting solution was mixed thoroughly and allowed to equilibrate by incubating at 37°C for 5 minutes.
3. Thereafter, 600 μ l of freshly prepared epinephrine was added to the reaction mixture.
4. The reaction mixture was read at 30 seconds interval for 150 seconds at 480 nm using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Model 752G, China).
5. The blank was treated the same way, except that 80 μ l of distilled water was used instead of serum.
6. The changes in absorbances of both test and blank were determined.
7. The percentage inhibition of auto-oxidation of epinephrine by SOD was calculated.
8. The serum SOD activity was expressed as U/ml.
9. One unit of SOD activity was equivalent to the amount of SOD that can cause 50% inhibition of epinephrine.

Calculation

% Inhibition = $\frac{\text{OD blank} - \text{OD test}}{\text{OD blank}} \times 100$ (%)

Enzyme Unit (U/ml) = $\frac{\% \text{ inhibition}}{50} \times \text{dilution factor}$. OD = Optical density

Estimation of Serum Glutathione Peroxidase (GPx) Activities

The activity of glutathione peroxidase (GPx) was determined using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Model 752G, China) according to the method of Rotruck *et al.*, (1993). Glutathione peroxidase catalyzes the oxidation of reduced glutathione (GSH) by hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) to form oxidized glutathione (GSSG) and water. The amount of GSH consumed is directly proportional to the activity of GPx and is expressed as U/ml (μmol of GSH consumed/minute). The remaining GSH reacts with 5,5'-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB) to produce a yellow complex that absorbs maximally at 412 nm.

Reagents Used

1. Phosphate buffer (pH 7.0)
2. Sodium azide
3. Reduced glutathione (GSH)
4. Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂)
5. 10% trichloroacetic acid (TCA)
6. 5,5'-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB)
7. GSH standard solution (0.651 μmol/ml)
8. Distilled water
9. Serum sample (test)

Procedure

1. The activity of glutathione peroxidase was determined by using UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Model 752G, China) according to the method of Rotruk *et al.*, (1993).
2. Glutathione peroxidase in the presence of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) oxidizes reduced glutathione (GSH) to form H₂O.
3. The amount of GSH consumed is directly proportional to the activity of GPx and it is expressed as U/ml (μmol of GSH consumed/minute).
4. The GSH remaining after the reaction was allowed to react with 5,5'-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB) to form a yellow complex that absorbs maximally at 412 nm.
5. The reaction mixture contained 0.4 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 0.1 ml sodium azide, 0.2 ml of plasma or standard or blank, 0.2 ml of glutathione, and 0.1 ml of H₂O₂.
6. The resulting solution was thoroughly mixed and incubated at 37°C for 10 minutes.
7. The reaction was arrested by the addition of 0.4 ml of 10% trichloroacetic acid (TCA).
8. The tubes were centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 5 minutes.
9. Thereafter, 0.5 ml of the supernatant was added into a clean test tube followed by 2 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and 0.5 ml of 40 mM DTNB.
10. The solution was thoroughly mixed and the resulting yellow colour was read at 412 nm.
11. A blank was treated the same way except that it contained 0.2 ml of distilled water instead of sample.
12. A standard solution of reduced glutathione (GSH) was prepared at a concentration of 20 mg per 100 ml, corresponding to 0.651 μmol/ml, and was used as a reference.
13. The activity of glutathione peroxidase was expressed as U/ml of plasma (μmoles of GSH utilised/minute).

Calculation

Actual Test OD = OD Blank – OD Test Actual Std OD = OD Std – OD Blank.

GPx activity = Actual OD Test/Actual OD STD X STD Concentration (U/mL).

Determination of Reduced Glutathione (GSH)

The level of reduced glutathione (GSH) was determined using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Model 752G, China) according to the method of Beutler *et al.* (1993). This method was based on the development of a yellow colour when 5,5'-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB) was added to compound containing sulphhydryl groups. The intensity of the colour developed was measured at 412 nm in a spectrophotometer and was proportional to the concentration of GSH in the sample.

Reagents Used

1. Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) solution
2. Precipitating reagent
3. Disodium hydrogen phosphate solution (0.3 M)
4. 5,5'-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB) reagent
5. Reduced glutathione (GSH) standard solutions (10 mg/dl and 20 mg/dl)
6. Distilled water
7. Serum sample

Procedure

1. Sample preparation: Two hundred microlitres (200 µl) of serum were mixed with 1.8 ml of EDTA solution.
2. Protein precipitation: 3.0 ml of precipitating reagent were added, mixed thoroughly, and allowed to stand for 5 minutes before centrifugation.
3. Filtrate preparation: After centrifugation, 2 ml of the filtrate were transferred into a clean test tube.
4. Reaction mixture: To the filtrate, 4 ml of 0.3 M disodium hydrogen phosphate solution and 1 ml of DTNB reagent were added.
5. Color development: The mixture was thoroughly mixed, and the yellow colour developed was measured at 412 nm using the UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Model 752G, China).
6. Standard preparation: Standard solutions containing 10 mg/dl and 20 mg/dl of reduced glutathione were treated in the same manner as the samples.
7. Expression of result: The values were expressed as mg/dl for plasma.

Calculation

Conc of GSH (umol/l) = OD test / ODstd X conc of standard

RESULT

Table 1.1: Effect of Dichlorvos and Ascorbic Acid on the Rat's Spleen Weight.

SPLEEN WEIGHT	Groups	Mean ± SEM	p-value	F-value
	A-Control	0.10 ± 0.000		1.000
	B-dichlorvos (0.1ml)	0.47 ± 0.367	0.548	
	C-dichlorvos (0.1ml)+ AA (0.1ml)	0.10 ± 0.000	1.000	
	D-0.1ml AA	0.10 ± 0.000	1.000	
	E-dichlorvos (0.1ml) + AA (0.4ml)	0.10 ± 0.000	1.000	
	F-AA (0.4ml)	0.10 ± 0.000	1.000	

Data were analyzed using One-way ANOVA, followed by PostHOC Turkey's multiple comparison, and data was considered significant at $P < 0.05$ (*= significant)

Table 1.1 above presents the analysis of the spleen weight of wistar Rats treated with ascorbic acid following dichlorvos (Dich) induced toxicity. The ANOVA result shows no statistically significant difference in the spleen weight.

Table 1.2: Effect of Dichlorvos and Ascorbic Acid on the Rat's Body Weight.

GROUPS	WEIGHT (g)	MEAN ± SEM	p-value
A-Control	Before admin	196.4 ± 1.97	
	After admin	233.4 ± 3.40	
B-dichlorvos (0.1ml)	Before admin	197.6 ± 3.31	0.244
	After admin	216.7 ± 6.93	
C- dichlorvos (0.1ml) + AA (0.1ml)	Before admin	251.4 ± 2.21	0.000*
	After admin	300.4 ± 5.69	
D-AA (0.1ml)	Before admin	233.3 ± 3.07	0.021*
	After admin	258.9 ± 4.59	
E-0.1ml dichlorvos + AA (0.4ml)	Before admin	236.2 ± 2.95	0.004*
	After admin	263.9 ± 5.03	
F-AA (0.4ml)	Before admin	245.5 ± 2.02	0.000*
	After admin	279.7 ± 5.36	

Data were analyzed using One-way ANOVA, followed by Post HOC Turkey's multiple comparison, and data was considered significant at $P < 0.05$ (*= significant)

Table 1.2: Presents the relative body weight of the wistar rats measured before treatment (Initial), and 24 hours after the final treatment (Final). The result of the ANOVA indicated that there were significant differences in the initial, final weight when compared to the control groups.

Table 1.3: Full Blood Count Analysis (WBC, LYM#, MID#, Lym% and Gran%).

Groups		Mean \pm SEM	p-value	F-value
WBC	A	1.38 \pm 0.09		0.931
	B	2.15 \pm 0.61	0.467	
	C	1.79 \pm 0.32	0.916	
	D	1.50 \pm 0.24	0.966	
	E	1.70 \pm 0.20	1.00	
	F	1.94 \pm 0.20	0.755	
LYM#	A	1.36 \pm 0.08		0.920
	B	2.12 \pm 0.61	0.468	
	C	1.76 \pm 0.03	0.915	
	D	1.48 \pm 0.24	0.970	
	E	1.67 \pm 0.21	1.000	
	F	1.91 \pm 0.21	0.763	
MID#	A	0.02 \pm 0.01		0.552
	B	0.03 \pm 0.01	0.979	
	C	0.02 \pm 0.00	0.999	
	D	0.01 \pm 0.00	0.979	
	E	0.01 \pm 0.01	0.979	
	F	0.02 \pm 0.00	1.000	
Lym%	A	98.73 \pm 0.72		0.384
	B	98.83 \pm 0.32	1.000	
	C	98.87 \pm 0.37	1.000	
	D	99.00 \pm 0.26	0.953	
	E	98.00 \pm 1.11	1.000	
	F	98.33 \pm 0.47	0.997	
Mid%	A	1.20 \pm 0.65		0.284
	B	1.07 \pm 0.29	1.000	
	C	0.80 \pm 0.21	0.943	
	D	0.77 \pm 0.15	0.960	
	E	0.83 \pm 0.15	0.922	
	F	0.93 \pm 0.13	0.990	
Gran%	A	0.07 \pm 0.07		0.894
	B	0.10 \pm 0.06	1.000	
	C	0.33 \pm 0.18	0.998	
	D	0.23 \pm 0.19	0.549	
	E	1.17 \pm 0.97	1.000	
	F	0.73 \pm 0.47	0.896	

Data were analyzed using One-way ANOVA, followed by Post HOC Turkey's multiple comparison, and data was considered significant at $P < 0.05$ (*= significant).

The result above shows the Mean \pm SEM values for WBC, Mid%, Lym%, Gran%, mid # and LYM#, there were are markable increase in group B which received dichlorvos when compared to the control in WBC, LYM#, Lym%, and mid# while the supplementation of ascorbic acid shows a decrease comparable to that of the control but was not significant. Mid% and Gran% shows a reduction among group with induction of the dichlorvos compared to group A. Across groups, total white blood cell count (WBC) show no statistical significance (p-values 0.467-1.000). Lymphocyte counts (LYM) mirror this pattern with p-values \geq 0.468. Putativemonocyte/eosinophil/basophil fraction (MID) is like wise unchanged (p \approx 0.979-1.000). Percent differentials (Lym%, Mid%, Gran%) show no significant contrasts with all p-values $>$ 0.549, indicating neither dichlorvos exposure nor ascorbic acid administration produced a measurable leukocytic differential shift.

Table 1.4: Full Blood Count Analysis (RBC, HGB, HCT, MCV and MCH).

Groups		Mean \pm SEM	p-value	F-value
RBC	A	7.31 \pm 0.02		1.865
	B	7.26 \pm 0.01	1.000	
	C	7.09 \pm 0.03	0.905	
	D	7.63 \pm 0.25	0.998	
	E	7.39 \pm 0.23	0.655	
	F	7.59 \pm 0.13	0.767	
HGB	A	12.43 \pm 0.15		1.892
	B	13.00 \pm 0.30	0.869	
	C	13.53 \pm 0.03	0.325	
	D	13.60 \pm 0.38	0.984	
	E	12.77 \pm 0.63	0.272	
	F	13.60 \pm 0.35	0.272	
HCT	A	0.42 \pm 0.00		0.432
	B	0.42 \pm 0.00	0.996	
	C	0.42 \pm 0.00	0.997	
	D	0.44 \pm 0.01	1.000	
	E	0.42 \pm 0.02	0.778	
	F	0.43 \pm 0.01	0.966	
MCV	A	57.07 \pm 0.12		1.716
	B	58.57 \pm 1.17	0.872	
	C	59.80 \pm 0.06	0.394	
	D	57.43 \pm 0.75	1.000	
	E	56.67 \pm 1.79	1.000	
	F	56.57 \pm 0.65	0.999	
MCH	A	17.07 \pm 0.20		5.902
	B	17.93 \pm 0.43	0.374	

	C	19.13 ± 0.88	0.119	
	D	17.83 ± 0.23	0.584	
	E	17.23 ± 0.47	1.000	
	F	17.90 ± 0.17	1.000	

Data were analyzed using One-way ANOVA, followed by Post HOC Turkey's multiple comparison, and data was considered significant at $P < 0.05$ (= significant)*

Table 1.4 above depicts the findings of the RBC, HGB, HCT, MCH and MCV, the present result shows that the induction of dichlorvos increased HGB, MCV and MCH activities and decreased the RBC and HCT as seen in group B when compared with group A, while supplementation of the Ascorbic acid shows a different level of reversal caused by the dichlorvos. Red blood cell count (RBC), hemoglobin (HGB), hematocrit (HCT), mean corpuscular volume (MCV) and mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) are stable across groups showing no significant difference across groups with $p \geq 0.272$, indicating that neither dichlorvos nor ascorbic acid significantly disrupted the overall mass and size of circulating red cells.

Table 1.5: Full Blood Count Analysis (MCHC, RDW-CV, RDW-SD, and PLT).

	Groups	Mean ± SEM	p-value	F-value
MCHC	A	299.00 ± 3.22		6.830
	B	306.33 ± 1.20	0.514	
	C	319.33 ± 1.45	0.004	
	D	310.67 ± 5.46	0.785	
	E	304.33 ± 2.60	0.120	
	F	316.33 ± 0.88	0.012	
RDW-CV	A	16.60 ± 0.10		2.831
	B	16.77 ± 0.43	0.998	
	C	16.07 ± 0.03	0.804	
	D	17.23 ± 0.55	0.343	
	E	17.50 ± 0.15	0.678	
	F	17.03 ± 0.18	0.903	
RDW-SD	A	32.23 ± 0.28		0.373
	B	33.47 ± 1.67	0.918	
	C	32.97 ± 0.07	0.991	
	D	33.57 ± 0.52	0.891	
	E	33.57 ± 1.19	0.891	
	F	32.70 ± 0.49	0.999	
PLT	A	619.0 ± 6.08		3.495
	B	670.0 ± 32.53	0.973	
	C	477.0 ± 12.5	0.367	

	D	615.7 ± 20.84	0.457	
	E	748.7 ± 105.86	1.000	
	F	677.7 ± 34.27	0.951	

Data were analyzed using One-way ANOVA, followed by Post HOC Turkey's multiple comparison, and data was considered significant at $P < 0.05$ (*= significant)

Table 1.5 shows the results of the MCHC, RDW-CV, RDW-SD and PLT, The comparison focuses on dichlorvos alterations and ascorbic interventions in the MCHC, RDW-CV, RDW-SD and PLT activities which shows a nonsignificant increase when group B is compared with Group A, For the MCHC the mean value in low vit. C + dichlorvos and high vit. C were higher than control vit. Suggesting that supplementation of ascorbic acid elevated hemoglobin concentration induced with dichlorvos. RDW-CV, RDW-SD and PLT mean \pm SEM values showed a dose dependent differences between group.

Table 1.6: Full Blood Count Analysis (MPV, PDW-CV, PCT, P-LCR, PDW-SD and GRANT#).

	Groups	Mean \pm SEM	p-value	F-value
MPV	A	7.73 \pm 0.03		2.277
	B	7.53 \pm 0.08	0.942	
	C	7.43 \pm 0.08	0.763	
	D	7.13 \pm 0.23	0.241	
	E	7.20 \pm 0.20	0.155	
	F	7.17 \pm 0.20	0.194	
PDW-CV	A	14.13 \pm 0.09		2.251
	B	14.07 \pm 0.21	1.000	
	C	14.03 \pm 0.15	0.999	
	D	13.43 \pm 0.17	0.504	
	E	13.67 \pm 0.24	0.149	
	F	13.73 \pm 0.20	0.650	
PCT	A	4.77 \pm 0.06		4.546
	B	5.03 \pm 0.21	0.986	
	C	3.54 \pm 0.10	0.099	
	D	4.41 \pm 0.28	0.733	
	E	5.35 \pm 0.59	0.951	
	F	4.86 \pm 0.17	1.000	
P-LCR	A	16.63 \pm 0.14		2.402
	B	15.53 \pm 0.94	0.963	
	C	15.13 \pm 0.61	0.877	
	D	12.93 \pm 1.27	0.217	
	E	13.27 \pm 1.24	0.150	

	F	13.30 ± 1.13	0.225	
PDW-SD	A	12.20 ± 0.17		1.728
	B	11.73 ± 0.32	0.967	
	C	11.47 ± 0.22	0.823	
	D	10.67 ± 0.48	0.376	
	E	10.97 ± 0.59	0.188	
	F	11.07 ± 0.58	0.459	
GRANT#	A	0.00 ± 0.00		0.910
	B	0.01 ± 0.00	0.987	
	C	0.01 ± 0.00	0.987	
	D	0.00 ± 0.00	0.464	
	E	0.02 ± 0.02	0.999	
	F	0.01 ± 0.01	0.808	

Data were analyzed using One-way ANOVA, followed by Post HOC Turkey's multiple comparison, and data was considered significant at $P < 0.05$ (*= significant).

The table 1.6 presents the results of the MPV, PDW-CV, PCT, P-LCR, PDW-SD and GRANT# level, The result in group B reflects deficits in the MPV, PDW-CV, P-LCR, and PDW-SD and an increase in PCT, and GRANT# due to dichlorvos toxicity. The intervention treatment with ascorbic acid in groups C, D, E, and F regulated their activity level of the parameters to a statistical non-significant level Table 4.8: Effect of Dichlorvos and Ascorbic Acid on Oxidative Stress Biomarkers.

MDA (nmol/ml)	Groups	Mean ± SEM	p-value	F-value
	A-Control	1.22 ± 0.107		7.636
	B-dichlorvos(0.1 ml)	2.39 ± 0.266	0.017*	
	C-dichlorvos(0.1ml)+ AA(0.1ml)	1.23 ± 0.231	1.000	
	D-0.1ml AA	0.92 ± 0.087	0.906	
	E-dichlorvos(0.1 ml) + AA(0.4ml)	1.54 ± 0.340	0.879	
	F-AA (0.4ml)	0.79 ± 0.024	0.706	
SOD (U/l)	A-Control	15.77 ± 0.59		31.791
	B-dichlorvos(0.1 ml)	7.17 ± 0.35	0.000*	
	C-dichlorvos(0.1ml)+ AA(0.1ml)	15.36 ± 1.29	0.999	
	D-0.1ml AA	17.05 ± 0.66	0.869	
	E-dichlorvos(0.1 ml) + AA(0.4ml)	9.61 ± 1.14	0.002*	
	F-AA (0.4ml)	18.89 ± 0.22	0.142	
CAT serum (U.l)	A-Control	46.13 ± 3.06		18.985
	B-dichlorvos(0.1 ml)	16.63 ± 1.42	0.001*	
	C-dichlorvos(0.1ml)+ AA(0.1ml)	52.25 ± 5.68	0.838	
	D-0.1ml AA	56.09 ± 2.86	0.437	
	E-dichlorvos(0.1 ml) + AA(0.4ml)	49.16 ± 5.23	0.990	
	F-AA (0.4ml)	62.50 ± 1.26	0.070	

Data were analyzed using One-way ANOVA, followed by Post HOC Turkey's multiple

comparison, and data was considered significant at $P < 0.05$ (= significant).*

Result of the descriptive analysis of the data gotten for MDA, SOD, and CAT shows the mean and SEM for all groups (table above), one-way ANOVA was done to check for significance and the result shows that there is statistical significance increase in group B of the activity level of MDA when compared to the control Group, while SOD And CAT presented a statistical significant decrease in group B (**dichlorvos**). Groups C-F when compared to group A shows statistical significance increase. 4.9

Histological Findings

A. Control group

PLATE A: A section of the splenic tissue with apparently normal spleen, with well-organised white pulp and red pulp regions. The white pulps (arrow) are prominent, displaying densely packed lymphocytes surrounding central arterioles. Similarly, the red pulp displays of splenic cords and splenic sinusoids (arrowhead) (H&E x 400)

B. Dichlorvos Group

PLATE B: Sections of the splenic tissue show the characteristic architecture of the spleen, with well-organised white pulp and red pulp regions. The white pulps (arrow) are prominent, displaying densely packed lymphocytes surrounding central arterioles. Similarly, the red pulp displays of splenic cords and splenic sinusoids (arrowhead) (H&E x 400)

C. Low Dose of Ascorbic Acid and Dichlorvos Group

PLATE C: Sections of the splenic tissue show the characteristic architecture of the spleen, with well-organised white pulp and red pulp regions. The white pulps (arrow) are prominent, displaying densely packed lymphocytes surrounding central arterioles. Similarly, the red pulp displays of splenic cords and splenic sinusoids (arrowhead) (H&E x 400).

D. Low Dose of Ascorbic Acid

PLATE D: Sections of the splenic tissue show the characteristic architecture of the spleen, with well-organised white pulp and red pulp regions. The white pulps (arrow) are prominent, displaying densely packed lymphocytes surrounding central arterioles. Similarly, the red pulp.

DISCUSSION

Dichlorvos, a commonly used organophosphate insecticide, is known to induce oxidative stress, hematological alterations, and splenic injury through the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and inhibition of acetylcholinesterase (Amali *et al.*, 2024). The spleen, an important organ involved in hematopoiesis and immune defense, is particularly vulnerable to oxidative damage. This study therefore evaluated the protective effects of ascorbic acid, a potent antioxidant, against dichlorvos-induced toxicity.

The results showed that rats exposed to dichlorvos alone exhibited increased oxidative stress, as indicated by elevated malondialdehyde (MDA) levels and reduced antioxidant enzyme activities such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT). Increased MDA levels indicate enhanced lipid peroxidation and cellular membrane damage caused by excessive ROS production (Ambali *et al.*, 2010; Lukaszewicz-Hussain, 2018). However, co-administration of ascorbic acid significantly reduced MDA levels and improved SOD and CAT activities, demonstrating its antioxidant capacity to neutralize free radicals and restore enzymatic defense systems (Nimse and Pal, 2015; Akinloye and Ighodaro, 2018; Afolabi *et al.*, 2021).

In terms of physiological parameters, dichlorvos exposure caused a slight reduction in body weight compared to the control group, suggesting systemic toxicity and possible metabolic disturbances due to acetylcholinesterase inhibition and oxidative stress (Ambali *et al.*, 2010). Rats treated with ascorbic acid alongside dichlorvos showed improved body weight, particularly at higher doses, indicating that vitamin C may support metabolism and reduce toxic effects by enhancing antioxidant defense and detoxification processes (Afolabi *et al.*, 2021). However, spleen weight did not show significant differences across the experimental groups, suggesting that the administered dose and duration of dichlorvos exposure did not produce marked splenic hypertrophy or atrophy.

Hematological findings revealed that dichlorvos exposure produced mild alterations in white blood cell and red blood cell indices, although most changes were not statistically significant. Slight increases in white blood cell counts in the dichlorvos-treated group may reflect an inflammatory or immune response to pesticide-induced oxidative stress (Ogunmodede *et al.*, 2019). Co-administration of ascorbic acid helped stabilize these hematological parameters, supporting its role in maintaining immune cell integrity and reducing leukocytic stress (El-Demerdash *et al.*, 2021).

Similarly, minor changes were observed in red blood cell parameters, including RBC, hematocrit, hemoglobin, and erythrocyte indices, which may indicate early erythrocyte stress caused by lipid peroxidation of red cell membranes (Olayemi and Oyewole, 2020). Treatment with ascorbic acid improved these values and helped maintain normal erythropoietic function, consistent with previous findings that vitamin C enhances red blood cell stability and supports iron metabolism (Farombi *et al.*, 2018).

Platelet indices also showed mild but non-significant variations among groups. The dichlorvos-treated group demonstrated slight increases in platelet counts, possibly due to compensatory responses to oxidative vascular stress. Ascorbic acid treatment restored platelet parameters closer to normal levels, indicating its protective effect against pesticide-induced hematological disturbances (Abdel-Wahhab *et al.*, 2018; Uchendu *et al.*, 2017).

Histological examination of the spleen further supported these findings. The control group displayed normal splenic architecture with well-organized white and red pulp regions. In contrast, the dichlorvos-only group showed distorted architecture, lymphoid depletion, and congestion of the red pulp sinusoids. Groups treated with ascorbic acid demonstrated progressive improvement in splenic structure, with the high-dose ascorbic acid group showing nearly normal histological features and preserved lymphoid follicles. These observations suggest that ascorbic acid effectively mitigates dichlorvos-induced structural damage to the spleen.

Overall, the findings of this study indicate that dichlorvos exposure induces oxidative stress and mild hematological disturbances, while ascorbic acid supplementation provides protective antioxidant effects that help maintain hematological stability and preserve spleen structure.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, dichlorvos administration caused significant oxidative stress, as evidenced by elevated serum MDA and reduced SOD and CAT levels. Ascorbic acid supplementation, especially at higher doses, effectively mitigated these effects, indicating its potent antioxidative role in protecting against pesticide-induced toxicity.

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